

Comparison of different on-farm wheat trial setups to help farmers' cultivar choice

Péter MIKÓ¹, Mihály FÖLDI², Mária MEGYERI¹, Gyula VIDA¹, Szilvia BENCZE², Judit FEHÉR², Dóra DREXLER²

¹Agricultural Institute, Centre for Agricultural Research, Martonvásár, Hungary

²Research Institute of Organic Agriculture (ÖMKi), Budapest, Hungary

E-mail: miko.peter@atk.hu

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The annual number of cultivars that could be tested on an organic farm is strongly limited in Hungary. To overcome this obstacle, the equivalent of an on-station trial (with 6 m² plots in 3 replications) was applied in the field of an organic farmer next to the farmer's large (0.1 ha) trial plots (collecting random samples from three 1 m² area) using the same set of winter wheat cultivars (2019: 8 cultivars, 2020: 7 cultivars).

Regression analyses resulted in significant ($p < 0.001$) moderate correlations ($0.45 < R^2 < 0.56$) between the values of the two trial types regarding protein and gluten contents, and Zeleny sedimentation value. Grain yield of cultivars harvested from the two plot types resulted in strong correlation ($R^2 = 0.60$, $p < 0.001$). The strength of these correlations increased up to $R^2 = 0.7$ in the case of protein and gluten contents when only the four common (regarding years) cultivars were analysed, while significant correlations were found around $R^2 = 0.55$ for their other traits. Grain yield and gluten content were higher in the small plot trial than in the samples collected from the farmer's plots, while Zeleny was higher in the farmer's samples. Results also showed that the quality measurement with NIR technology is reliable only in the case of protein content (at least in a relative sense), because there was very little difference ($0.9 \pm 5.2\%$) between the two trial types.

Based on the comparison of the ranks of the cultivars in the two trial types, the best (regarding protein and gluten contents) and the worst (regarding grain yield) performing groups of cultivars were the same. Therefore, a small plot trial can be recommended for testing the quality of numerous cultivars in an organic farm using NIR measurement, while, for grain yield, a negative selection can be made in the same trial. After two years of such testing, a few selected cultivars could be put in the on-

farm yield trial for one year in order to define the final rank of the cultivars for the given organic farm.

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